

Smarandache friendly numbers-another approach

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Abstract One approach to Smarandache friendly numbers is given by A. Murthy, who defined them Ref [1]. Another approach is presented here.

Keywords Smarandache friendly numbers.

Smarandache friendly numbers were defined by A. Murthy [1] as follows.

Definition 1. If the sum of any set of consecutive terms of a sequence is equal to the product of first and last number, then the first and the last numbers are called a pair of Smarandache friendly numbers.

Here, we will consider a sequence of natural numbers.

1. It is easy to note that (3, 6) is a friendly pair as $3 + 4 + 5 + 6 = 18 = 3 \cdot 6$.

2. By elementary operations and trial, we can find such pairs, but as magnitude of natural numbers increases, this work becomes tedious. Hence an algorithm is presented here.

Assume that (m, n) is a pair of friendly numbers, $n > m$, so that

$$m + (m + 1) + (m + 2) + \cdots + n = m \cdot n.$$

Let $n = m + k$, where k is a natural number. Then the above equation becomes

$$m + (m + 1) + (m + 2) + \cdots + n = m \cdot (m + k).$$

On simplification, this gives,

$$k^2 + k - 2(m^2 - m) = 0.$$

That is,

$$k = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 8(m^2 - m)}}{2},$$

considering the positive sign only.

Now, k will be a natural number only if $1 + 8(m^2 - m)$ is a perfect square of an odd natural number.

For $m = 3$, we have $k = 3$, so that $n = 3 + 3 = 6$, and then $(3, 6)$ are friendly numbers as we observed earlier.

For $m = 5$, $k = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{161}}{2}$, which is not an integer. Hence k does not exist for every m .

For $m = 15$, $k = 20$, hence $n = 35$. So the next pair of friendly numbers is $(15, 35)$. Other pairs are $(85, 204)$ and $(493, 1189)$.

At the end, the list of m and $1 + 8(m^2 - m)$ is given using a computer software.

2. If (m, n) is a friendly pair, of natural numbers, then it is conjectured that $(m + 2n, 2m + 5n - 1)$ is also a friendly pair.

Since, $(3, 6)$ and $(15, 35)$ are friendly pairs, we have $3x + 6y = 15$ and $3p + 6q = 35$, for some x, y, p, q being natural numbers. These equations are true for $x = 1, y = 2, p = 2$ and $q = 5$. With 1 to be subtracted from second equation.

These solutions are unique, hence this conjecture.

This suggests that there are infinite pairs of friendly natural numbers.

Definition 2. [1] x and y are primes. They are called Smarandache friendly primes if the sum of any set of consecutive primes, whose first term is x and last is y , is equal to their product $x \cdot y$.

Example. $(2, 5), (3, 13), (5, 31)$ are pairs of friendly primes, for $3 + 5 + 7 + 11 + 13 = 39 = 3 \cdot 13$.

Since the primes are not uniformly distributed, an algorithm for friendly primes seems to be impossible.

4. For various sequences, different pairs of friendly numbers can be obtained.

The values of $m \leq 1000$ and $1 + 8(m^2 - m)$ are given below. Those with perfect squares are underlined. Only four pairs were obtained.

1	1.0000	2	4.1231	<u>3</u>	<u>7.0000</u>	4	9.8489	5	12.6886
6	15.5242	7	18.3576	8	21.1896	9	24.0208	10	26.8514
11	29.6816	12	32.5115	13	35.3412	14	38.1707	<u>15</u>	<u>41.0000</u>
16	43.8292	17	46.6583	18	49.4874	19	52.3163	20	55.1453
21	57.9741	22	60.8030	23	63.6318	24	66.4605	25	69.2892
26	72.1180	27	74.9466	28	77.7753	29	80.6040	30	83.4326
31	86.2612	32	89.0898	33	91.9184	34	94.7470	35	97.5756
36	100.4042	37	103.2327	38	106.0613	39	108.8899	40	111.7184
41	114.5469	42	117.3755	43	120.2040	44	123.0325	45	125.8610
46	128.6895	47	131.5181	48	134.3466	49	137.1751	50	140.0036
51	142.8321	52	145.6606	53	148.4891	54	151.3176	55	154.1460
56	156.9745	57	159.8030	58	162.6315	59	165.4600	60	168.2884
61	171.1169	62	173.9454	63	176.7739	64	179.6023	65	182.4308
66	185.2593	67	188.0877	68	190.9162	69	193.7447	70	196.5731

71	199.4016	72	202.2301	73	205.0585	74	207.8870	75	210.7155
76	213.5439	77	216.3724	78	219.2008	79	222.0293	80	224.8577
81	227.6862	82	230.5146	83	233.3431	84	236.1716	85	239.0000
86	241.8284	87	244.6569	88	247.4854	89	250.3138	90	253.1423
91	255.9707	92	258.7992	93	261.6276	94	264.4561	95	267.2845
96	270.1129	97	272.9414	98	275.7698	99	278.5983	100	281.4267
101	284.2552	102	287.0836	103	289.9120	104	292.7405	105	295.5689
106	298.3974	107	301.2258	108	304.0543	109	306.8827	110	309.7112
111	312.5396	112	315.3680	113	318.1965	114	321.0249	115	323.8534
116	326.6818	117	329.5103	118	332.3387	119	335.1671	120	337.9956
121	340.8240	122	343.6524	123	346.4809	124	349.3093	125	352.1378
126	354.9662	127	357.7946	128	360.6231	129	363.4515	130	366.2799
131	369.1084	132	371.9368	133	374.7653	134	377.5937	135	380.4221
136	383.2506	137	386.0790	138	388.9074	139	391.7359	140	394.5643
141	397.3928	142	400.2212	143	403.0496	144	405.8781	145	408.7065
146	411.5349	147	414.3634	148	417.1918	149	420.0202	150	422.8487
151	425.6771	152	428.5056	153	431.3340	154	434.1624	155	436.9908
156	439.8193	157	442.6477	158	445.4761	159	448.3046	160	451.1330
161	453.9615	162	456.7899	163	459.6183	164	462.4467	165	465.2752
166	468.1036	167	470.9321	168	473.7605	169	476.5889	170	479.4174
171	482.2458	172	485.0742	173	487.9026	174	490.7311	175	493.5595
176	496.3879	177	499.2164	178	502.0448	179	504.8733	180	507.7017
181	510.5301	182	513.3585	183	516.1870	184	519.0154	185	521.8439
186	524.6723	187	527.5007	188	530.3292	189	533.1576	190	535.9860
191	538.8145	192	541.6429	193	544.4713	194	547.2997	195	550.1282
196	552.9566	197	555.7850	198	558.6135	199	561.4419	200	564.2703
201	567.0988	202	569.9272	203	572.7556	204	575.5840	205	578.4125
206	581.2409	207	584.0693	208	586.8978	209	589.7262	210	592.5546
211	595.3831	212	598.2115	213	601.0399	214	603.8683	215	606.6968
216	609.5252	217	612.3536	218	615.1821	219	618.0105	220	620.8389
221	623.6674	222	626.4958	223	629.3242	224	632.1526	225	634.9811
226	637.8095	227	640.6379	228	643.4664	229	646.2948	230	649.1232
231	651.9517	232	654.7801	233	657.6085	234	660.4370	235	663.2654
236	666.0938	237	668.9222	238	671.7507	239	674.5791	240	677.4075
241	680.2360	242	683.0644	243	685.8928	244	688.7213	245	691.5497
246	694.3781	247	697.2065	248	700.0350	249	702.8634	250	705.6918
251	708.5203	252	711.3487	253	714.1771	254	717.0056	255	719.8340
256	722.6624	257	725.4908	258	728.3193	259	731.1477	260	733.9761
261	736.8046	262	739.6330	263	742.4614	264	745.2899	265	748.1183
266	750.9467	267	753.7751	268	756.6036	269	759.4320	270	762.2604

271	765.0889	272	767.9173	273	770.7457	274	73.5742
275	776.4026	276	779.2310	277	782.0594	278	784.8879
279	787.7163	280	790.5447	281	793.3732	282	796.2016
283	799.0300	284	801.8585	285	804.6869	286	807.5153
287	810.3438	288	813.1722	289	816.0006	290	818.8290
291	821.6575	292	824.4859	293	827.3143	294	830.1428
295	832.9712	296	835.7996	297	838.6281	298	841.4565
299	844.2849	300	847.1133	301	849.9418	302	852.7702
303	855.5986	304	858.4271	305	861.2555	306	864.0839
307	866.9124	308	869.7408	309	872.5692	310	875.3976
311	878.2261	312	881.0545	313	883.8829	314	886.7114
315	889.5398	316	892.3682	317	895.1967	318	898.0251
319	900.8535	320	903.6819	321	906.5103	322	909.3387
323	912.1672	324	914.9956	325	917.8240	326	920.6525
327	923.4809	328	926.3093	329	929.1378	330	931.9662
331	934.7946	332	937.6230	333	940.4515	334	943.2799
335	946.1083	336	948.9368	337	951.7652	338	954.5936
339	957.4221	340	960.2505	341	963.0789	342	965.9073
343	968.7358	344	971.5642	345	974.3926	346	977.2211
347	980.0495	348	982.8779	349	985.7064	350	988.5348
351	991.3632	352	994.1917	353	997.0201	354	999.8485
355	1002.6769	356	1005.5054	357	1008.3338	358	1011.1622
359	1013.9907	360	1016.8190	361	1019.6475	362	1022.4759
363	1025.3043	364	1028.1328	365	1030.9612	366	1033.7897
367	1036.6180	368	1039.4465	369	1042.2749	370	1045.1034
371	1047.9318	372	1050.7603	373	1053.5886	374	1056.4171
375	1059.2455	376	1062.0740	377	1064.9023	378	1067.7307
379	1070.5592	380	1073.3876	381	1076.2161	382	1079.0444
383	1081.8729	384	1084.7013	385	1087.5298	386	1090.3582
387	1093.1866	388	1096.0150	389	1098.8435	390	1101.6719
391	1104.5004	392	1107.3287	393	1110.1572	394	1112.9856
395	1115.8141	396	1118.6425	397	1121.4709	398	1124.2993
399	1127.1278	400	1129.9562	401	1132.7847	402	1135.6130
403	1138.4415	404	1141.2699	405	1144.0984	406	1146.9268
407	1149.7552	408	1152.5836	409	1155.4120	410	1158.2405
411	1161.0688	412	1163.8973	413	1166.7257	414	1169.5542
415	1172.3826	416	1175.2111	417	1178.0394	418	1180.8679
419	1183.6963	420	1186.5248	421	1189.3531	422	1192.1816
423	1195.0100	424	1197.8385	425	1200.6669	426	1203.4954
427	1206.3237	428	1209.1522	429	1211.9806	430	1214.8091

431	1217.6375	432	1220.4659	433	1223.2943	434	1226.1228
435	1228.9512	436	1231.7797	437	1234.6080	438	1237.4365
439	1240.2649	440	1243.0933	441	1245.9218	442	1248.7501
443	1251.5786	444	1254.4070	445	1257.2355	446	1260.0638
447	1262.8923	448	1265.7207	449	1268.5492	450	1271.3776
451	1274.2061	452	1277.0344	453	1279.8629	454	1282.6913
455	1285.5198	456	1288.3481	457	1291.1766	458	1294.0050
459	1296.8335	460	1299.6619	461	1302.4904	462	1305.3187
463	1308.1472	464	1310.9756	465	1313.8041	466	1316.6324
467	1319.4608	468	1322.2893	469	1325.1177	470	1327.9462
471	1330.7745	472	1333.6030	473	1336.4314	474	1339.2599
475	1342.0883	476	1344.9167	477	1347.7451	478	1350.5736
479	1353.4020	480	1356.2305	481	1359.0588	482	1361.8873
483	1364.7157	484	1367.5442	485	1370.3726	486	1373.2010
487	1376.0294	488	1378.8579	489	1381.6863	490	1384.5148
491	1387.3431	492	1390.1716	493	1393.0000	494	1395.8284
495	1398.6569	496	1401.4852	497	1404.3137	498	1407.1421
499	1409.9706	500	1412.7990	501	1415.6274	502	1418.4558
503	1421.2843	504	1424.1127	505	1426.9412	506	1429.7695
507	1432.5980	508	1435.4264	509	1438.2549	510	1441.0833
511	1443.9117	512	1446.7401	513	1449.5686	514	1452.3970
515	1455.2255	516	1458.0538	517	1460.8823	518	1463.7107
519	1466.5391	520	1469.3676	521	1472.1959	522	1475.0244
523	1477.8528	524	1480.6813	525	1483.5096	526	1486.3381
527	1489.1665	528	1491.9950	529	1494.8234	530	1497.6519
531	1500.4802	532	1503.3087	533	1506.1371	534	1508.9656
535	1511.7939	536	1514.6224	537	1517.4508	538	1520.2793
539	1523.1077	540	1525.9362	541	1528.7645	542	1531.5930
543	1534.4214	544	1537.2499	545	1540.0782	546	1542.9066
547	1545.7351	548	1548.5635	549	1551.3920	550	1554.2203
551	1557.0488	552	1559.8772	553	1562.7057	554	1565.5341
555	1568.3625	556	1571.1909	557	1574.0194	558	1576.8478
559	1579.6763	560	1582.5046	561	1585.3331	562	1588.1615
563	1590.9900	564	1593.8184	565	1596.6469	566	1599.4752
567	1602.3037	568	1605.1321	569	1607.9604	570	1610.7889
571	1613.6173	572	1616.4458	573	1619.2742	574	1622.1027
575	1624.9310	576	1627.7595	577	1630.5879	578	1633.4164
579	1636.2448	580	1639.0732	581	1641.9016	582	1644.7301
583	1647.5585	584	1650.3870	585	1653.2153	586	1656.0438
587	1658.8722	588	1661.7007	589	1664.5291	590	1667.3575

591	1670.1859	592	1673.0144	593	1675.8428	594	1678.6711
595	1681.4996	596	1684.3280	597	1687.1565	598	1689.9849
599	1692.8134	600	1695.6417	601	1698.4702	602	1701.2986
603	1704.1271	604	1706.9554	605	1709.7839	606	1712.6123
607	1715.4408	608	1718.2692	609	1721.0977	610	1723.9260
611	1726.7545	612	1729.5829	613	1732.4114	614	1735.2397
615	1738.0682	616	1740.8966	617	1743.7250	618	1746.5535
619	1749.3818	620	1752.2103	621	1755.0387	622	1757.8672
623	1760.6956	624	1763.5240	625	1766.3524	626	1769.1809
627	1772.0093	628	1774.8378	629	1777.6661	630	1780.4946
631	1783.3230	632	1786.1515	633	1788.9799	634	1791.8083
635	1794.6367	636	1797.4652	637	1800.2936	638	1803.1221
639	1805.9504	640	1808.7789	641	1811.6073	642	1814.4357
643	1817.2642	644	1820.0925	645	1822.9210	646	1825.7494
647	1828.5779	648	1831.4063	649	1834.2347	650	1837.0631
651	1839.8916	652	1842.7200	653	1845.5485	654	1848.3768
655	1851.2053	656	1854.0337	657	1856.8622	658	1859.6906
659	1862.5190	660	1865.3474	661	1868.1759	662	1871.0043
663	1873.8328	664	1876.6611	665	1879.4895	666	1882.3180
667	1885.1464	668	1887.9749	669	1890.8032	670	1893.6317
671	1896.4601	672	1899.2886	673	1902.1169	674	1904.9454
675	1907.7738	676	1910.6023	677	1913.4307	678	1916.2592
679	1919.0875	680	1921.9160	681	1924.7444	682	1927.5729
683	1930.4012	684	1933.2297	685	1936.0581	686	1938.8866
687	1941.7150	688	1944.5433	689	1947.3718	690	1950.2002
691	1953.0287	692	1955.8571	693	1958.6855	694	1961.5139
695	1964.3424	696	1967.1708	697	1969.9993	698	1972.8276
699	1975.6561	700	1978.4845	701	1981.3130	702	1984.1414
703	1986.9698	704	1989.7982	705	1992.6267	706	1995.4551
707	1998.2836	708	2001.1119	709	2003.9403	710	2006.7688
711	2009.5972	712	2012.4257	713	2015.2540	714	2018.0825
715	2020.9109	716	2023.7394	717	2026.5677	718	2029.3962
719	2032.2246	720	2035.0531	721	2037.8815	722	2040.7100
723	2043.5383	724	2046.3668	725	2049.1953	726	2052.0237
727	2054.8521	728	2057.6804	729	2060.5090	730	2063.3374
731	2066.1658	732	2068.9941	733	2071.8225	734	2074.6511
735	2077.4795	736	2080.3079	737	2083.1362	738	2085.9648
739	2088.7932	740	2091.6216	741	2094.4500	742	2097.2786
743	2100.1069	744	2102.9353	745	2105.7637	746	2108.5923
747	2111.4207	748	2114.2490	749	2117.0774	750	2119.9060

751	2122.7344	752	2125.5627	753	2128.3911	754	2131.2195
755	2134.0481	756	2136.8765	757	2139.7048	758	2142.5332
759	2145.3618	760	2148.1902	761	2151.0186	762	2153.8469
763	2156.6755	764	2159.5039	765	2162.3323	766	2165.1606
767	2167.9893	768	2170.8176	769	2173.6460	770	2176.4744
771	2179.3030	772	2182.1313	773	2184.9597	774	2187.7881
775	2190.6167	776	2193.4451	777	2196.2734	778	2199.1018
779	2201.9302	780	2204.7588	781	2207.5872	782	2210.4155
783	2213.2439	784	2216.0725	785	2218.9009	786	2221.7292
787	2224.5576	788	2227.3862	789	2230.2146	790	2233.0430
791	2235.8713	792	2238.7000	793	2241.5283	794	2244.3567
795	2247.1851	796	2250.0137	797	2252.8420	798	2255.6704
799	2258.4988	800	2261.3271	801	2264.1558	802	2266.9841
803	2269.8125	804	2272.6409	805	2275.4695	806	2278.2979
807	2281.1262	808	2283.9546	809	2286.7832	810	2289.6116
811	2292.4399	812	2295.2683	813	2298.0969	814	2300.9253
815	2303.7537	816	2306.5820	817	2309.4106	818	2312.2390
819	2315.0674	820	2317.8958	821	2320.7241	822	2323.5527
823	2326.3811	824	2329.2095	825	2332.0378	826	2334.8665
827	2337.6948	828	2340.5232	829	2343.3516	830	2346.1802
831	2349.0085	832	2351.8369	833	2354.6653	834	2357.4939
835	2360.3223	836	2363.1506	837	2365.9790	838	2368.8076
839	2371.6360	840	2374.4644	841	2377.2927	842	2380.1211
843	2382.9497	844	2385.7781	845	2388.6064	846	2391.4348
847	2394.2634	848	2397.0918	849	2399.9202	850	2402.7485
851	2405.5771	852	2408.4055	853	2411.2339	854	2414.0623
855	2416.8909	856	2419.7192	857	2422.5476	858	2425.3760
859	2428.2046	860	2431.0330	861	2433.8613	862	2436.6897
863	2439.5183	864	2442.3467	865	2445.1750	866	2448.0034
867	2450.8318	868	2453.6604	869	2456.4888	870	2459.3171
871	2462.1455	872	2464.9741	873	2467.8025	874	2470.6309
875	2473.4592	876	2476.2878	877	2479.1162	878	2481.9446
879	2484.7729	880	2487.6016	881	2490.4299	882	2493.2583
883	2496.0867	884	2498.9153	885	2501.7437	886	2504.5720
887	2507.4004	888	2510.2288	889	2513.0574	890	2515.8857
891	2518.7141	892	2521.5425	893	2524.3711	894	2527.1995
895	2530.0278	896	2532.8562	897	2535.6848	898	2538.5132
899	2541.3416	900	2544.1699	901	2546.9985	902	2549.8269
903	2552.6553	904	2555.4836	905	2558.3123	906	2561.1406
907	2563.9690	908	2566.7974	909	2569.6257	910	2572.4543

911	2575.2827	912	2578.1111	913	2580.9395	914	2583.7681
915	2586.5964	916	2589.4248	917	2592.2532	918	2595.0818
919	2597.9102	920	2600.7385	921	2603.5669	922	2606.3955
923	2609.2239	924	2612.0522	925	2614.8806	926	2617.7092
927	2620.5376	928	2623.3660	929	2626.1943	930	2629.0227
931	2631.8513	932	2634.6797	933	2637.5081	934	2640.3364
935	2643.1650	936	2645.9934	937	2648.8218	938	2651.6501
939	2654.4788	940	2657.3071	941	2660.1355	942	2662.9639
943	2665.7925	944	2668.6208	945	2671.4492	946	2674.2776
947	2677.1062	948	2679.9346	949	2682.7629	950	2685.5913
951	2688.4197	952	2691.2483	953	2694.0767	954	2696.9050
955	2699.7334	956	2702.5620	957	2705.3904	958	2708.2188
959	2711.0471	960	2713.8757	961	2716.7041	962	2719.5325
963	2722.3608	964	2725.1895	965	2728.0178	966	2730.8462
967	2733.6746	968	2736.5032	969	2739.3315	970	2742.1599
971	2744.9883	972	2747.8167	973	2750.6453	974	2753.4736
975	2756.3020	976	2759.1304	977	2761.9590	978	2764.7874
979	2767.6157	980	2770.4441	981	2773.2727	982	2776.1011
983	2778.9294	984	2781.7578	985	2784.5864	986	2787.4148
987	2790.2432	988	2793.0715	989	2795.9001	990	2798.7285
991	2801.5569	992	2804.3853	993	2807.2136	994	2810.0422
995	2812.8706	996	2815.6990	997	2818.5273	998	2821.3560
999	2824.1843	1000	2827.0127				

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